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DETERMINATION OF THE PROPERTIES AND COMPOSITION OF OIL, GAS AND CONDENSATE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF WELLS BY DUAL COMPLETION

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the properties and compositions of oil, gas and condensate to determine their heterogeneity during their jointly separate operation by the method of dual completion (DC). In order to successfully implement the DC method simultaneously in gas reservoirs in one and in another second elevator of oil reservoirs in one well, comparative laboratory analyses and field studies on the properties and compositions of oil, gas and condensate were carried out, which determine a significant role in the development of wells dual completion.

Keywords: methane, nitrogen, carbon dioxide, asphalt, sulfur, paraffin, free gases.

Simultaneous development of several formations by one object is possible only with the same physical and chemical properties of oils in the combined formations, if the inflow of oil and gas is sufficient from each formation at an acceptable bottom-hole pressure in the well, with close values of reservoir pressure in the combined formations, excluding oil flows between the layers, and close values of reservoir waterlogging. If the above conditions are not met, then multidimensional deposits are developed by the DC method with one well [1].

At the Altyguyi deposit in the NK₉ horizon, free gases contain 97.90% methane, up to 1.19% of its homologues, up to 0.70% nitrogen and 0.21% carbon dioxide.

In the NK_{7g} horizon, free gases contain 97.20% methane, up to 1.54% of its homologues, 0.67% nitrogen and 40.17% carbon dioxide.

In the NK₈ horizon, free gases contain 97.20% methane, up to 2.08% of its homologues, 0.55% nitrogen and 0.17% carbon dioxide. The oil of the NK₉ horizon has a density of 0.9065 g / cm³, solidifies at a temperature of +33 °C, the viscosity at a temperature of 50 °C is 51.69 Pz, and at a temperature of 20 °C does not flow.

Up to a temperature of 300 °C, it boils by 19%. The composition contains 4.7% asphaltene, 16.7% resins, 21.4% paraffin and 0.41% sulfur.

According to the group hydrocarbon composition, they belong to the methane-naphthenic geochemical type (H: M 0.99), contain 13% aromatic, 43.3% naphthenic and 43.7% methane hydrocarbons.

The density of condensates of the NK_{7g} horizon is 0.7 0.53 g / cm³, solidify -3 °C, viscosity at a temperature of 20 °C 1.79 Pz. Up to a temperature of 300 °C, boil up to 77%.

According to the group hydrocarbon composition, they belong to the methane-naphthenic geochemical type. (H: M 0.83), contain 9.0% aromatic, 41.7% naphthenic and 49.3% methane hydrocarbons (Table 1.2).

The density of condensates of the NK₉ horizon is 0.7971 g/cm³, they solidify at a temperature equal to +3 °C, the viscosity at a temperature of 20 °C is 1.8 s Pz. Up to a temperature of 300 °C, up to 76% is boiled off. The composition contains 1.4 resin, 3.5% paraffin and asphaltene is absent. By group composition, they belong to the methane-naphthenic geochemical type (H:0.84) and contain 9.9% aromatic, 41.2% naphthenic and 48.9% methane hydrocarbons.

Table 1

Properties and composition of the gas
(average value over the horizons)

Horizon	Interval Perforations, (m)	Density		Quantity, % volume			
		g/l	by air	CO ₂	Nitrogen	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₆
Soluble gases							
NK-9	3670-3680	0,742	0,574	0,21	0,70	97,90	1,60
Free gases							
NK -7d	3512-3624	0,738	0,571	0,22	0,67	97,57	0,94
NK -8	3616-3625	0,737	0,570	0,17	0,55	97,20	1,14

Table 2

Properties and composition of the gas
(average value over the horizons)

Horizon	Interval Perforations, (m)	Количество, % объем					
		C ₃ H ₈	C ₄ H ₁₀		C ₅ H ₁₂		C ₆ +above
			izo	nor	izo	nor	
Soluble gases							
NK-9	3670-3680	0,32	0,06	0,07	0,02	0,01	-
Free gases							
NK -7d	3512-3624	0,30	0,08	0,13	0,05	0,05	-
NK -8	3616-3625	0,62	0,07	0,17	0,05	0,05	-

According to the conducted studies from wells 1,2,5,6,7,8, and 9 samples of reservoir waters under laboratory conditions, their chemical and physical properties were determined. The selected reservoir water

samples belong to depths of 3546-3771 m and correspond to the lower deposits of the red-colored strata of the NK₇-NK₉ horizons (Tables 3 and 4).

Table 3

Properties and composition of reservoir waters

Well number	Horizon	Depth interval, m	Density g/cm ³ pH	Composition mg/l, mg-equivalent/l		
				Cl	SO ₄	HCO ₃
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	NK -8	3616-3625	1,016	15546	0	805
			7,7	438	0	13
2	NK -8- NK -9	3546-3659	1,019	17753	1056	1763
			8,1	500	22	29
5	NK -7d	3618-3624	1,010	8787	0	525
			8,2	248	0	9
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6	NK -9	3690-3694 3700-3703	1,039	31092	352	976
			7,3	876	7	16
7	NK -9	3746-3750	1,027	21629	96	2135
			7,1	609	2	35
7	NK -9	3768-3771	1,035	28389	96	1586
			7,0	800	2	26
8	NK -7d	3660-3662	1,020	20277	1120	427
			7,5	571	23	7
8	NK -8	3732-3734	1,015	14870	160	769
			8,2	419	3	13
8	NK -9		1,040	20277	160	488
			6,7	571	3	8
9	NK -8		1,036	29233	160	1403
			7,5	823	3	23

Formation waters with chlorine calcium have a hydrocarbonatium and sulfonate sodium appearance and salinity properties from 15 to 50 g/l [2, 3].

The weakest mineralized sodium bicarbonate waters with a salt content of 15 g/l on the convex part of

the structure, and highly mineralized chlorocalcium brines are found in the reclinal part of the structure.

Such hydrochemical properties of reservoir waters are also found in the approximate deposits of Altygyu. These patterns are associated with tectonic disturbances.

Table 4

Properties and composition of reservoir waters

Well number	Horizon	Depth interval, m	Composition mg/l, mg-equivalent/l			Amount mg/l	Type of water
			Ca	Mg	Na+K		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	NK -8	3616-3625	401	0	9913	26665	Oil+condensate
			20	0	431		
2	NK -8 NK -9	3546-3659	808	0	11753	33139	Water+Oil
			40	0	501		
5	NK -7d	3618-3624	90	18	5750	15170	Gas+condensate+Oil
			5	2	250		
6	NK -9	3690-3694	1202	730	17917	52269	Oil+condensate
		3700-3703	60	60	779		
7	NK -9	3746-3750	641	486	13202	38189	Oil+condensate
			32	40	574		
7	NK -9	3768-3771	882	632	16836	48421	Oil+condensate
			44	52	732		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
8	NK -7d	3660-3662	801	291	12351	35267	Oil+condensate
			40	24	537		
8	NK -8	3732-3734	401	243	9085	25528	Oil+condensate
			20	20	395		
8	NK -9	3777-3781	3607	0	9246	33778	Oil+condensate
			180	0	402		
9	NK -8	3519-3521	1202	632	16951	49571	Oil+condensate
			60	52	737		

The hydrochemical properties of the structure of the Altyguyi deposit make it possible to assert a high degree of oil and gas content of the lower part of the red-colored strata and the underlying rocks.

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